

Adaptive beamformer with Generalized Sidelobe Canceler for Plane Wave Ultrasound Image

Larissa Comar Neves
Federal University of Technology
- Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0003-1268-326X

Acácio José Zimbico
Eduardo Mondlane University
Maputo, Mozambique
ORCID: 0000-0002-2181-6426

Joaquim Miguel Maia
Federal University of Technology
- Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-6309-8664

Danilo Fernandes Gomes
Federal University of Technology
- Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-8740-657X

Amauri Amorin Assef
Federal University of Technology
- Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-2001-5387

Fábio Kurt Schneider
Federal University of Technology
- Paraná
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-6916-1361

Eduardo Tavares Costa
State University of Campinas
Campinas, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-6787-5205

Abstract— Methods for adaptive beamforming have obtained positive results improving the quality of medical ultrasound images compared to the non-adaptive technique Delay and Sum (DAS). Generalized Sidelobe Canceler (GSC) can considerably improve the lateral resolution of medical ultrasound images, but the contrast of the image is not satisfactory. The Eigenspace-Based Minimum Variance beamformer (EBMV) is an adaptive beamformer that can suppress a large part of the noise and provide images with higher contrast and resolution in comparison with DAS and Minimum Variance beamformer (MVB). In this work, it was applied Eigenspace-Based Generalized Sidelobe Canceller Beamformer to plane wave ultrasound images. All the simulated echo data was obtained from Plane Wave Challenge in Medical Ultrasound Imaging (PICMUS) website. The data were acquired using a Verasonics Vantage 256 equipment using a L11-4v 128 elements transducer. The results obtained were compared with DAS and MVGSC and have shown improvement of lateral resolution.

Keywords— *generalized sidelobe canceller; eigenspace-based beamforming; resolution; plane wave.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The adaptive beamformer technique has been widely used in ultrasound imaging because it can significantly improve axial resolution and contrast [1]. The adaptive filtering technique was presented by Capon [2] and is extensively studied until today. Adaptive beamformer is a method that can improve signal quality due to its capacity to maintains the desired signal and reduces noise and interference.

The Generalized Sidelobe Canceler (GSC) method can separate the signal into an adaptive and a non-adaptive component. This allows the suppression of part of interference and noise, improving the axial resolution. However, the contrast does not show satisfactory improvement [1].

The Eigenspace-Based beamformer allows to divide the covariance matrix into two subspaces, one as function of the received signal and another as function of the noise. Thus, it is possible to design the Minimum Variance (MV) weights for the built signal subspace, maintaining the desired signal and reducing the contribution of sidelobe signals [1].

In this paper, we will approach the generalized eigenspace-based sidelobe canceler, which relates the subspace of the signal to the weight vector GSC, thus eliminating still more interference and noise signals.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Signal and Array Model

Considering a standard linear array of M elements, the output of a beamformer is given by [1]:

$$y(k) = w(k)^H X(k) = \sum_{m=1}^M w_m^*(k) x_m(k), \quad (1)$$

where k is the discrete time index, $X(k)$ is the time-delayed version of array received signals observations $X(k) = [x_1(k); x_2(k); \dots; x_M(k)]^T$, $w(k) = [w_1(k); w_2(k); \dots; w_M(k)]^T$ is a complex vector of weights, $[]^T$ is the transpose, $*$ is the complex conjugate and $()^H$ denotes the Hermitian Matrix [3].

B. Minimum Variance (MV) Beamformer

For adaptative beamformers the $X(k)$ can be represented as in (2) [4]:

$$X(k) = S(k) + P(k), \quad (2)$$

where $S(k)$ is the echo signal received and the $P(k)$ represents the interference and noise signals.

For MV beamformer we assume that $S(k)$ is uncorrelated to $P(k)$, so the weights of the MV beamformer are determined minimizing the variance of the beamformer output under the constraint, as in (3) [4]:

$$w_{MV} = \arg \min w^H R w, \text{ subject to } w^H a = 1 \quad (3)$$

The optimal weight vector of MV beamformer is given as in (4) [5]:

$$w_{MV} = \frac{R^{-1} a}{a^H R^{-1} a} \quad (4)$$

where a is the steering vector with $1 \times M$ and R is the data covariance matrix (CM), which can be found dividing the echo data into overlapped submatrices X_l . The subarray upper limit is $L \leq M/2$. The estimate of R after averaging can be represented as in (5) [6]:

$$R = \frac{1}{(2K+1)(M-L+1)} \sum_{k=-K}^K \sum_{l=1}^{M-L+1} X_l(k) X_l(k)^H, \quad (5)$$

where $(2K+1)$ is the number of data samples used to estimate the CM R .

In order to improve stability and robustness, a diagonal loading technique can be applying as in (6) [2]:

$$R = R + \varepsilon I = R + \frac{1}{\Delta * L} \text{tr}\{R\}I, \quad (6)$$

where $\text{tr}\{ \}$ is the trace of sample CM, and Δ is a constant that varies from 10 to 100 [2].

III. METHOD

The proposed method in this work uses the GSC with the Eigenspace-Based Minimum Variance beamformer (EBMV).

A. Generalized Sidelobe Canceler (GSC)

The generalized sidelobe canceler, originally proposed by Applebaum and Chapman [7], is calculated by minimizing the output power of the adaptative beamformer in terms of Linearly Constrained Minimum Variance (LCMV) [8].

The GSC weight is separated into two orthogonal components, the adaptive power w_a , and the non-adaptive power w_q . This form can suppress the interference and noise signal of echo data.

The weight vector can be expressed as [3]:

$$w_{GSC} = w_q - Bw_a \quad (7)$$

$$w_q = (aa^H)^{-1}a \quad (8)$$

$$w_a = (B^H RB)^{-1} B^H R w_q \quad (9)$$

where B is the blocking matrix of dimensions $M \times (M-1)$ such that: $(a^H B = 0)$.

B. Eigenspace-Based (EB) Beamformer

In the Eigenspace-Based beamformer, the CM R is decomposed to a signal subspace (E_s) and a noise subspace (E_p) as in (10) [9].

$$R = U \Lambda U^H = E_s + E_p, \quad (10)$$

where $\Lambda = \text{diag}[\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_L]$, in which $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_L$ are the eigenvalues in descending order, and $U = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_L]$, in which $v_i, i = 1, \dots, L$ are the orthogonal eigenvectors.

The signal subspace E_s is determined using the eigenvectors corresponding to the first largest eigenvalues, where the main lobe contributed energy is concentrated. The eigenvectors used to construct the signal subspace E_s depends of the weight coefficient δ , that we set, where $\lambda_i \geq \delta \lambda_1$ [2]. Thus, the weight vector of the Eigenspace-Based beamformer with Generalized Sidelobe Canceler (EBGSC) is calculated as in (11):

$$w_{EBGSC} = E_s E_s^H w_{GSC} \quad (11)$$

In the next section we show the results of the proposed method.

C. Image data acquisition

The simulation was performed with Plane Wave Challenge in Medical Ultrasound Imaging (PICMUS) database. The data were acquired using a 128 elements transducer (L11-4v) with central frequency of 5.2 MHz. All image data acquisition (simulated, phantom and human *in vivo*) includes transmission of 75 plane waves firing elements with steering angles spaced uniformly between -16.0° to $+16.0^\circ$, with 0.5° step, and the central wave angle equal to 0° .

The PICMUS database results of the challenge organized during IEEE IUS 2016, where a framework was proposed to evaluate the performance of algorithms to reconstruct ultrasound images from direct plane wave transmission, respecting the ethics committee rules for *in vivo* acquisitions. This information can be accessed on the PICMUS website [10].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the simulation of resolution distortion beamformer responses of 10 plane waves for (a) DAS technique with 128 active elements, (b) MVGSC ($L = 64, K = 0, \Delta = 20$) and (c) EBGSC ($L = 64, K = 0, \Delta = 20, \delta = 0.2$).

Fig. 2 shows the lateral resolution calculated from simulated signal in Fig. 1. It was observed that the EBGSC images resolution decreased in points of lower intensity. For the results obtained with the simulated phantom used to evaluate the contrasts, presented in Fig. 3, the Contrast Ratio (CR) was calculated using the background region showed in Fig.4 and the values are presented graphically in Fig. 5. The CR was calculated as in (12):

$$CR = \left| \varphi_{cyst} - \varphi_{back} \right| \quad (12)$$

where φ_{cyst} and φ_{back} are the mean amplitude (before log-compression) in the phantom cyst and background, respectively.

In Fig. 5 it is possible to see that the contrast in the MVGSC and EBGSC is higher than the DAS, and the EBGSC is the highest value. The values of the contrast are 30.90 dB, 34.79 dB and 34.89 dB for DAS, MGSC and EBGSC, respectively.

The ESGSC method is relatively new and few articles were found to compare the results. In [2], this technique shown an improvement in lateral resolution and a contrast increase of 16.77 dB and 26.73 dB when compared with MGSC and DAS respectively. The parameters used were: $M = 64$, with a central frequency of 3.33 MHz, $L = 32, K = 0, \Delta = 20$ and $\delta = 0.2$. Also, in [4], there is a significant improvement in lateral resolution and a contrast increase of 0.73 dB and 2.2 dB compared to MGSC and DAS, respectively. The parameters used were: $M = 128$, with a central frequency of 6.25 MHz, $L = 64, K = 0, \Delta = 20$ and $\delta = 0.2$.

In all these cases, an improvement in resolution and contrast is shown, reinforcing the need for research using the EBGSC technique.

Fig. 1. Beamformer responses of 10 plane waves for (a) DAS technique with 128 active elements, (b) MVGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$) and (c) EBGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$, $\delta = 0.2$). This image corresponds to the simulation of the resolution distortion test, from PICMUS database [10].

Fig. 2. Lateral resolution of 10 plane waves, comparing DAS, MVGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$) and EBGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$, $\delta = 0.2$) at $z = 20.12$ mm.

Fig. 3. Beamformer responses of 10 plane waves for (a) DAS technique with 128 active elements, (b) MVGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$) and (c) EBGSC ($L = 64$, $K = 0$, $\Delta = 20$, $\delta = 0.2$). The image corresponds to the simulation of contrast-speckle test from PICMUS database [10].

Fig. 4. Region used to calculate the CR.

Fig. 5. Contrast ratio for simulated circular anechoic cysts, shown on Fig. 3, for DAS, MVGSC and EBGSC beamformers.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, it was applied a GSC weight vector to the EBMV. The MVGSC and EBGSC methods presented significant improvement of the image when compared to the traditional DAS method. The EBGSC and MVGSC have shown improvement in contrast when comparing to the DAS and, in the simulation of the resolution distortion, the EBGSC presented better lateral resolution, further reducing noise and interference signals.

Analyzing the obtained results, it was possible to conclude that EBGSC has been effective in improving lateral resolution and contrast and may be better studied for image enhancement.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Brazilian Agencies CAPES, CNPq, Fundação Araucária, FINEP and Ministry of Health for the financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.-F. Synnevåg, A. Austeng, and S. Holm, "Minimum Variance Adaptive Beamforming Applied to Medical Ultrasound Imaging," in Proc. IEEE Ultrason. Symp., Sept. 2005, v. 2, pp. 1199–1202.
- [2] J. Li, X. Chen, Y. Wang, W. Li, D. Yu, "Eigenspace-Based Generalized Sidelobe Canceller Beamforming Applied to Medical Ultrasound Imaging," Sensors, v. 16, n° 8, pp. 1192–2003, 2016.
- [3] B. M. Asl, "Eigenspace-Based Minimum Variance Beamforming Applied to Medical Ultrasound Imaging," IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics and Frequency Control, v. 57, n°11, pp. 2381–2390, 2010.
- [4] N. T. Schiefler, J. M. Maia, F. K. Schneider, A. J. Zimbico, A. A. Assef, and E. T. Costa, "Generation and analysis of ultrasound images using plane wave and sparse arrays techniques," Sensors, v. 18, n. 11, pp. 3660–3683, 2018.
- [5] S. Aliabadi, Y. Wang, J. Yu, "Adaptive Scaled Wiener Postfilter Beamformer ultrasound imaging," URSI Asia-Pacific Radio Science Conference, August 21–25, 2016, Seoul, Korea.
- [6] J. F. Synnevåg, A. Austeng, and S. Holm, "Benefits of minimum variance beamforming in medical ultrasound imaging," IEEE transactions on ultrasonics, ferroelectrics, and frequency control, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 1868–1879, 2009.
- [7] X. Zeng, Y. Wang, J. Yu, and Y. Guo, "Correspondence-beam domain eigenspace-based minimum variance beamformer for medical ultrasound imaging," IEEE transactions on ultrasonics, ferroelectrics, and frequency control, vol. 60, no. 12, pp. 2670–2676, 2013.
- [8] S. Applebaum and D. Chapman, "Adaptive arrays with main beam constraints," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 650–662, 1976.
- [9] X. Zeng, C. Chen, Y. Wang, "Eigenspace-based minimum variance beamformer combined with Wiener postfilter for medical ultrasound imaging," Ultrasonics, vol. 52, p.996-1004, 2012.
- [10] H. Liebgott, A. Rodriguez-Molares, F. Cervenansky, J. A. Jensen, O. Bernard, "Plane-wave imaging challenge in medical ultrasound," In: IEEE. Ultrasonics Symposium (IUS), 2016 IEEE International. [S.l.], pp. 1–4, 2016.